

Ammonia based membrane
reactor for green Hydrogen

Welcome to this **third ANDREAH newsletter!**

ANDREAH is a four-year European project, whose main objective is to provide a quantum leap in the development of advanced ammonia decomposition technologies to produce ultra-pure hydrogen (>99.998%) by developing an innovative system based on a Catalytic Membrane Reactor (CMR) for the cracking of Ammonia. In this way, optimised heat management, improved conversion per pass and purification/recycling for more cost-efficient and resource-effective ammonia decomposition at lower temperatures compared to conventional systems will be achieved.

The present newsletter is the third release of the biannual letter that will be published by AndreaH presenting the progress on the project and highlighting information

related to the R&D fields addressed. Hope you will find the info in this newsletter interesting.

On our website www.andreahproject.eu you will find public presentations, all the public deliverables of the project and many other interesting news. Stay tuned!

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About the Project

ANDREAH is clustered around 3 phases, which will allow the smooth and sound transition from current development stage of the technologies to a validation at TRL 5.

As shown in the below picture, the ANDREAH methodology comprises upstream R&D activities of the proposed technologies, followed by selection and development of the final prototype.

Finally, the validation of the main selected technology will take place and the main KPIs for hydrogen production from NH_3 will be analysed.

Phase 1 – R&D (M1-M24): led by the universities, RTOs and industrial partners, this Phase is mainly focus on the optimization of key building blocks (Membranes, catalysts, sorbents and Reactors). Most of the experiments during this phase are performed at laboratory or small scale. The key components in this phase will be developed by TEC (membranes), CNR and UMI (Catalysts), and TUE (sorbents and reactors).

The main research areas that are explored within the R&D phase of ANDREAH, as well as how we will go beyond the state of the art, are explained in detail below, following the key components of the concept.

Moreover, this R&D phase is organised into three different pillars:

- The first pillar includes modelling activities (by TUE) to guide R&D partners on the best combination of catalyst, sorbents, reactors and membranes to guide the experiments in an effective way.
- In the second pillar, experiments with H_2 and NH_3 process that are well known for the R&D partners will be carried out first to validate the modelling.
- Gradually, R&D partners will move towards third pillar, where they will perform experiments combining different components together, as well as more complex streams based on the knowledge acquired in the first and second pillars.

A Design of Experiment approach will be used to find the best combination of parameters and processing routes for the different key components. This will reduce drastically the number of experiments needed in order to find the optimal combination of key building blocks.

The final outcome of Phase 1 will be the selection of the key components for their scale up in Phase 2. However, R&D on lower TRL components will also be made within the project to obtain direct indications on alternative solutions (up to TRL4).

ReCup Dissemination Activities

Looking back to the last months, the partners of ANDREAH project were very busy on their work and activities.

- **ANDREAH at 3rd SoAE:**

Within ANDREAH project, Dr. Valentina Cechetto from TU/e presented her results: the *3rd Symposium on Ammonia Energy*, held in China from September 22nd and 26th 2024.

- **ANDREAH at 19th NPS:**

Valentina Cechetto presented her results within ANDREAH project at the *19th edition of the Symposium of Netherlands Process Technology (NPS19)* held in Groningen on 8th and 9th October 2024. This prestigious gathering is a hub for academics, engineers, and industry professionals dedicated to revolutionizing process engineering.

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- **ANDREAH at EHW:**

Rina-C participated in the prestigious European Hydrogen Week held in Brussels last November from 20th to 24th 2024, an event that brought together key players in the energy sector to discuss the latest advancements in renewable energy technologies.

- **ANDREAH at 2nd Winter School**

The 2nd Edition of the Winter School on Membranes and Membrane Reactors took place on January 27th and 28th in Eindhoven, within 3 projects, ANDREAH, APOLO and MEASURED project, bringing together researchers, students, and experts in the field for an insightful and engaging two-day event.

The Winter School was a fantastic opportunity to deepen knowledge on membrane technology and its applications while networking with peers and renowned professionals.

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Professors and researchers presented their latest work, showcasing advancements and innovations in membrane reactors. Above all, within ANDREAH Project, our experts were: Dr. C. Italiano from CNR-ITAE, Dr. A. Pacheco from Tecnalia, P. Pinto and Roberta Montesano from RINA-C.

All the presentations, videos and program from the event can be found at <https://www.andreahproject.eu/winter-school-2025/>

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Consortium Meeting

Last 29th January 2025, the ANDREAH Project marked another significant milestone with its **M18 Consortium Meeting**, held at the innovative 1CUBE facilities in Eindhoven (NL).

The M18 Consortium Meeting not only marked significant progress for the ANDREAH Project, but also reinforced the strong bonds within the consortium. With a clear path forward and a shared commitment to innovation, the team is poised to achieve even greater milestones in the months ahead.

Followed up with **M18 Project Review Meeting of ANDREAH project**, where we showcased to the Project Officers from CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency and Clean Hydrogen Partnership our progresses, key achievements, future activities and plans.

M24 Consortium Meetings hosted by Umicore marked officially the halfway of our 48-month journey to continue with exciting progress, strong collaboration and ambitious goals.

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Meet our researcher: Minju Thomas

Minju Thomas, from CNR-ITAE of Messina is a post-doctoral fellow in Fuel Processing Materials and Technologies group (FPMAT).

In 2022, she joined at CNR-ITAE as a postdoctoral fellow and has been active in developing electrode materials and prototypes of flexible supercapacitors. Her research interests include the molecular-level modification of catalytic materials for energy generation and storage applications.

In 2023, she began working with FPMAT group in ANDREAH project. She is developing structured catalysts using Triply Periodic Minimal surface (TPMS) Ni-alloy supports for ammonia decomposition reaction and make them suitable in membrane-based reactors for long-term hydrogen generation. She is also involved in synthesis of new catalyst formulations and their kinetic modelling to better understand the reaction mechanisms at low temperatures.

Recently, she presented her latest research findings at the International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies (ICSET) held in the picturesque setting of Lipari, Italy. Her presentation, titled *"Magnesium doped lanthanum nickelate perovskites for ammonia decomposition: kinetic analysis at low temperatures"*, was part of her ongoing work within the ANDREAH project, a multidisciplinary initiative focused on advancing the development of renewable energy and hydrogen technologies for a sustainable energy future.

At ICSET, an internationally renowned forum for scientists and engineers in the energy sector, Minju shared key outcomes of her research, which contributes directly to the ANDREAH project's mission of creating efficient and innovative solutions in energy conversion and storage. The conference provided an excellent platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration, and Minju's presentation received enthusiastic interest from both academic and industry experts. Her participation also highlighted the vital role Italian research institutions like CNR-ITAE are playing in the global transition toward sustainable and renewable energy systems.

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What's next?

Don't miss our next events in OCTOBER:

➤ **SEPTech Conference**

www.septechconference.com

➤ **WORKSHOP on “Ammonia as Energy Carrier”**

Workshop: “Ammonia as Energy Carrier” (PART II)

organized by

- AMB_{H₂}
- AndreaH
- APOLO

Clean Hydrogen Partnership

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CUBE

24th October, 2025

8.30- 13:00

Microlab, Kastanjelaan 400, 5616 LZ Eindhoven, NL

ON-LINE (streaming via Teams)

Participation to the event is free. Registration is compulsory. Online streaming options are available.

<https://www.andreahproject.eu/workshop-october-2025/>

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Project Acronym: ANDREAH

Call: HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2

Starting date: July 1st 2023

Duration: 48 months

UE funding: 2,980,361 Euro

Coordinator: Fundación Tecnalia Research & Innovation

Project Coordinator: José-Luis Viviente, Jaione Ollo Loinaz

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